

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Preparation of the Reagent.—The thioamide was prepared from phenyl oxamide according to the method described by Reissert (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 3716). The reagent is soluble in alcohol, acetone, chloroform, etc. and in alkali and it melts at 176° after crystallisation from alcohol.

Detection.—The alcoholic solution of the reagent gives precipitates with a large number of cations. Mercuric mercury gives a yellow precipitate, while mercurous salts give a yellow precipitate which becomes grey on standing. Silver and lead give black precipitates. Cadmium and bismuth precipitates are yellow and brown respectively, obtained from faintly ammoniacal medium, while the zinc salt is white and antimony (trivalent) brick-red. Copper gives a violet precipitate soluble in mineral acids, in excess of ammonia, and partly in hot water. The brownish black precipitate of the cobaltous complex is soluble in mineral acids and in excess of alkali. The yellowish brown precipitate of the nickel complex shows similar properties. The copper complex is stable up to 70°, the cobalt complex up to 230° and nickel up to 160°.

Precipitation Limit for Copper, Cobalt and Nickel.—(i) One part of copper in 750,000 parts of water; using alcoholic solution of the reagent and a drop of sodium acetate solution.

(ii) One part of cobalt in 400,000 parts of water with neutral solution of the reagent followed by a drop of very dilute HCl.

(iii) One part of nickel in 2,000,000 parts of water with alcoholic solution of the reagent and a drop of dilute ammonia.

Copper Salt of the Reagent.—Copper sulphate (1 g.) and sodium acetate (4 g.) were dissolved in 1000 c.c. water and to the solution was added with stirring, a 1% alcoholic solution of the reagent in excess when copper was precipitated as a violet salt. This was filtered, washed with water and alcohol and then dried *in vacuo* over sulphuric acid. [Found: C, 37.0; H, 3.06; N, 10.7; S, 12.5; Cu, 24.4, 24.44. (C₈H₈N₂OS) CuH₂O requires C, 37; H, 3.08; N, 10.8; S, 12.33; Cu, 24.47 per cent].

Estimation of Copper.—A solution of Kahlbaum's reagent quality copper sulphate was prepared and standardised by the electrolytic method. A known amount of copper solution was neutralised with dilute ammonia and then sodium acetate (2 g.) was added to the just acidic solution. The solution was then diluted to 150-160 c.c. and to it was added at room temperature, drop by drop, with stirring, a 1% alcoholic solution

of the reagent in excess. The violet copper salt was allowed to settle, and then filtered and washed with water and alcohol. The precipitate was dried and ignited to oxide. The oxide was dissolved in nitric acid and titrated iodometrically in the usual way. The results are given below.

TABLE I.

Copper			Copper		
Taken.	Found.	Error.	Taken.	Found.	Error.
0.00776 g.	0.00775	-0.00001	0.01941	0.01940	-0.000009
0.01552	0.01552	Nil	0.02190	0.02190	Nil
0.01552	0.01552	-0.00004	0.03462	0.03461	-0.00001
			0.03462	0.03460	-0.00002

Cobalt Salt of the Thioamide.—The brownish black precipitate of the cobalt complex was obtained by adding a dilute solution of the sodium salt of the reagent to a cobalt solution and then adding, drop by drop, a dilute 2*N*-hydrochloric acid to the hot solution till the precipitate just coagulated. This was filtered, washed with water and alcohol and then dried in air. [Found: N, 9.02; Co, 18.95. (C₈H₆N₂OS) Co, 4H₂O requires N, 9.06; Co, 19.0 per cent].

Estimation of Cobalt.—A solution of Kahlbaum's reagent quality nickel free cobalt chloride solution was prepared and its strength was determined by estimating as cobalt sulphate. To a solution of cobalt chloride was added an excess of sodium salt of the reagent (1 g. of the reagent per 100 c.c. solution). It was then diluted to 200 c.c. and heated to boiling. To the hot solution was then added 2*N*-hydrochloric acid, drop by drop with stirring, till the precipitate just coagulated. The brownish black precipitate was then allowed to settle, filtered hot and washed with hot water. This was then dried, ignited to oxide and then converted to anhydrous sulphate. The results are given below.

TABLE II.

Cobalt			Cobalt				
Taken.	Found.	Error.	Taken.	Found.	Error.		
0.01168 g.	0.01168 g.	0.0307 g.	Nil.	0.02336	0.02338	0.0014	+0.00002
0.01168	0.01171	0.0308	+0.00003	0.028032	0.02804	0.0737	+0.000008
0.018688	0.01868	0.0491	-0.000008	0.03504	0.03504	0.0921	Nil

Nickel Salt of Thioamide.—The yellowish brown nickel compound was obtained by adding an alcoholic solution of the reagent to the solution

of a nickel salt, rendered alkaline with dilute ammonia. The solution was heated to boiling and then filtered and washed with water and alcohol. The air-dried salt was then analysed. [Found: N, 10'31; Ni, 21'49. ($C_8H_8N_2OS$) Ni, $2H_2O$ requires N, 10'26; Ni, 21'52 per cent].

Estimation of Nickel.—A solution of Kahlbaum's reagent quality nickel chloride was prepared and standardised by dimethylglyoxime method. To a solution of nickel chloride an excess of 1% alcoholic solution of the reagent was added and the mixture rendered alkaline with dilute ammonia. The solution was then diluted to 200 c.c. and heated to boiling. The precipitate was allowed to settle, filtered hot and washed with hot water. The precipitate was dried and gently ignited to oxide. The results are given below.

TABLE III.

Nickel		Ni	Error.	Nickel		Ni	Error.
Taken.	Found.	oxide.		Taken.	Found.	oxide.	
0'01124 g.	0'01132 g.	0'0144 g.	+0'00008	0'04496	0'04486	0'0571	-0'0001
0'02248	0'02248	0'0286	Nil	0'05620	0'05626	0'0716	+0'00006
0'03372	0'03379	0'0430	+0'00007	0'06744	0'06744	0'0858	Nil
				0'07868	0'07868	0'1001	Nil

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